

D8.5 Layman terms’ paper on the exposome pathways towards health effects

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2. Summary

This deliverable includes a description of the Equal-Life project in layman terms. For this we made use of two previously published articles in GOV open access and a developed animation.

3. Introduction

The audience for this deliverable is everyone interested in children's mental health, their cognitive development in relation to physical and social exposures during lifetime. In the past year several products have been developed and published to reach out to those interested in Equal-Life. This includes two open access papers published in the GOV open access Journal, targeting stakeholder and the general public.

GOV open access paper 1: "Studying the exposome concept for a healthier future for all children", published online May 27 2022. Online available at <https://www.openaccessgovernment.org/studying-the-exposome-concept-for-a-healthier-future-for-all-children/136663/>

GOV open access paper 2: "Equal-Life team: Improving child exposome and quality of life", published online October 14 2022. Online available at <https://doi.org/10.56367/OAG-036-10295>

Besides, an animation has been developed by the Equal-Life team. This animation video provides in about 3 minutes a short explanation of the exposome concept as used in Equal-Life, including the physical exposome, social exposome, and internal exposome. Next, the aim of the project is explained: how the exposome affects mental health and cognitive development in young children. The animation can be used for any outreaching activities, e.g. at conferences, but also in the recruitment of children (below 11y with guidance of an adult).

Subtitles of the animation have been made available in English, Spanish, Catalan, German, Dutch, Italian, Finnish, and Swedish; to accommodate for all languages where the in-depth studies are taking place.

Equal-Life animation video, online available at www.equal-life.eu

4. Online publications

4.1 Studying the exposome concept for a healthier future for all children

Studying the exposome concept for a healthier future for all children

Dr. Irene van Kamp, from the National Institute for Public Health and the Environment, discusses the exposome concept to study the role of the environment in human disease

Mental health is the result of complex interplay between genetic, psychological, environmental factors and experiences. The exposome concept, referring to the totality of exposures from conception onwards, is emerging as a very promising approach to studying the role of the environment in human disease.

The EU funded [Equal-Life project](#), which is part of the [European Human Exposome Network](#) employs the exposome concept in an integrated study of multiple exposures in relation to a child's development and life course mental health. A novel approach is used which looks at exposure data at a high spatial and temporal resolution combining physical and social aspects to understand influences on mental health and cognitive development at different ages and developmental stages. The goal is to propose the best supportive environments for children.

Mental Health is of growing concern

Mental ill health is one of the fastest growing public health issues in Europe and awareness about this has increased. Its contribution to the burden of disease weighs heavily on societies and economies. In Europe, the cost of mental ill health was estimated to be over 4% of GDP¹ in 2018. Children's mental ill health predicts to a large extent mental ill health in later life with impacts on quality of life and work situation. It is therefore of growing concern that at school age, one in ten children has a mental health problem that warrants support and treatment. These figures vary in time. More recently, for example, research shows that there is mixed evidence that children and adolescents have experienced significant anxiety and depression during the coronavirus pandemic and that these symptoms increased as compared to the pre-pandemic period.

Sensitivity and Child development

Children are sensitive for a whole range of social and physical influences from the moment they are conceived up until adulthood. Not because they are vulnerable per se, but because they are in a sensitive period for their development. As mental health, neurodevelopment is also affected by complex interplay between genetic, psychological, environmental factors and experiences. This has become painfully visible during the pandemic as well: there is growing evidence that the Covid-19 situation has had strong effects on children's development. There are claims that the environmental changes associated with the pandemic have negatively affected infant and child cognitive development. These effects would be stronger in children born into lower socio economic families. Underlying causes one could think of are parental stress,

lack of parental attentiveness, lack of physical activity, poor indoor climate, anxiety and depression, lack of guidance, crowding, chaotic circumstances all together forming the child's exposome.

What is the exposome and why is it important?

The exposome is an umbrella term for all the environmental exposures throughout the life course of a person. It encompasses all types of exposures. Some exposures arise from internal and external processes at individual level (e.g., smoking, diet, physical activity, infectious agents, psychosocial stress, parental support). Other exposure sources are shared at population level (e.g., climate, air quality, built environment, green space, noise and social capital). The exposome concept serves as a counterpart of the human genome and strives to map every exposure an individual is subjected to from conception to death, providing a DNA-like detailed level of exposure information.

Equal-Life discerns the external (physical, social) and internal exposome. The physical exposome is directly related to the description of the state of the environment - such as green spaces, sound and air quality, access to high quality and safe public spaces and playgrounds.

The social exposome focuses the social and psychosocial environment as well as on social (in)equities on mental health and cognitive development. This pertains to (in)equities in exposure distribution and accumulation across generations, vulnerability to exposures and potential equity impacts of urban (planning) policies on different societal groups.

Internal exposome is a consequence of external exposome filtered by personal vulnerabilities and lifestyle. It is measured in the person and can include biomarkers (i.e., indicators of exposure, susceptibility or outcome) but can also include processes that happen in the body and that can be analysed as a whole. Biomarkers are biological indicators measurable in saliva, hair, blood or urine. A well-known example is cortisol as a marker of stress.

The exposome contains a vast number of possible exposures during various phases of life. To reduce the complexity and make the broadness of the concept manageable, Equal-Life poses the questions: what is needed for a child /person to realise his or her own potential? What setting (e.g., kindergarten, school, recreational and sports facilities) and activities are relevant in view of mental health and development and at what age/life phase? From this we assess the possible mechanisms linking the exposome to mental health and cognitive development. Key mechanisms studied are stress and restoration, sleep and self-regulation.

How do we study this?

For a distinct set of outcomes related to cognition, mental symptoms and behaviour, well-being and diagnosed mental illnesses, the role of the exposome and underlying mechanisms is studied by making use of data from almost 250.000 EU children.

What will we do with this knowledge?

Equal-Life will develop and test interventions, such as improving housing environment, based on results of analyses and in close collaboration

with stakeholders. Interventions and best practices will be included in a tool and a guidance document primarily aimed at context specific policies that affect children in Europe, thus contributing to healthier environments for European children. Intervention at an early age could benefit society as a whole by enhancing mental health and education outcomes, thus also addressing the contextual and root causes of social inequalities.

The EU Charter of Fundamental Rights states: The EU and EU countries must respect, protect and promote children's rights. All EU policies that have an impact on children must be designed in line with the best interests of the child. Compliance to this will depend heavily on national and local policy actions as well. Our tools will therefore primarily be aimed at them.

Reference: 1 Gross Domestic Product

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4.2 Equal-Life team: Improving child exposome and quality of life

Equal-Life team: Improving child exposome and quality of life

Four PhD students from the Equal-Life team discuss their areas of research into the child exposome, looking at the environment children are raised in and the effects it has on mental health and cognitive development

Christoph Giehl

Roos Teeuwen

Sammie Jansen

Vasileios Milias

The [Equal-Life project](#), looks at early exposures during childhood through an integrated study of external social and physical and internal factors to understand cognitive development and mental health later on in life.

As part of the [European Human Exposome Network](#) the Equal-Life project team aims to propose the best environments for children to grow up in, as quality of life, social relations and interactions and their physical surroundings can effect their development and mental health later in life.

While some exposures come from internal and external processes at the individual level, like passive smoking or a poor diet, other exposures can affect entire population sizes – as seen with the COVID-19 pandemic and climate change. These exposures can also be intensified by existing inequalities like poverty.

The Equal-Life team aims to develop new solutions to improving mental health, such as bettering the housing environment and contributing to healthier outdoor environments for European children. They prioritise intervention at an early age, as improving child mental health can improve society through the eradication of social inequalities, and vice versa.

When it comes to the work you're doing on child exposome, what are your key objectives?

Christoph Giehl: My main topic is “statistical research methods” and so-called “measurement errors” in social-, human-, and health- research. A problem with this is that if our measures are biased, our results might be biased as well if we don't come up with statistical methods which are

able to “correct” those biases. When working with biomarkers (e.g., certain hormone levels measured from blood samples), this is usually less of a problem since we can expect those biomarkers to be rather objective. However, in Equal-Life apart from biomarkers, self-reported as well as measured indicators of mental health and cognitive development are available. My key objective when working on child exposome is to develop statistical methods and model frameworks which can adjust for potential biases, for example when mothers don't want to share that they smoked or drank alcohol during pregnancy, or children who do not want to share that they get bullied in school etc. As a result, we can reach less biased measures and estimates of child exposome and mental health outcomes and thus less biased results which will represent the reality better.

Roos Teeuwen: My key objective is to create new ways to measure children's exposure to urban green spaces so that they match better with children's preferences and day-to-day lives. Urban green spaces include parks, fields, and bushes. Many people of any age living in cities feel a strong desire to have green spaces in their everyday environments. We know how children love playing and socialising in green environments, not only around their homes but also near their schools, and that the expectations they have of such spaces vary with age. However, in the way that cities measure the value of their greenspaces this variance is not yet accounted for.

Sammie Jansen: The objectives of my PhD research are to provide an overview of the ethical aspects and societal implications of child exposome research in the mental health domain.

For this, it is important to understand what kinds of results the Equal-Life project aims for, what the possible consequences of these results are, and examine the possible normative implications thereof. For my research, I study the ethics literature on topics related to exposome research, conceptually and normatively analysing the expected implications of exposome research. I also discuss the possible ethical implications with researchers and stakeholders using interviews and focus groups.

Vasileios Milias: My focus within the Equal-Life project is to identify and measure the characteristics of the urban environment that could be used as indicators of potential

exposures (for instance, being exposed to noise, air pollution, and other individuals). I study the concept of accessibility, a term simple to use but complex to define and measure, and I am puzzled by what "easy access" to a place could or should reflect. This "easiness" is often translated to travelling time, cost, or distance. But could it also be translated to exposures that affect people's mental health? Arguably, a 10-minute walk through a dark, scary alley is not the same as a 10-minute walk through a vibrant street with many trees and flowers. My objective is to revisit existing accessibility methods and enrich them while accounting for exposures that influence people's mental health.

What have you discovered in the connection between child mental health and quality of life?

Christoph: For the analyses, we saw a high connection between the two concepts, meaning that the higher the quality of life, the better mental health can be. It is when analysing this relationship in more detail that things get complicated. Even though we can see a connection, not all children with "good" mental health are exposed to high quality of life, children with "bad" mental health can still report high quality of life, and so on. Therefore, there might be other factors affecting the relationship between the two concepts? Maybe child mental health is nested within the quality of life concept? These are the actual questions we are researching right now. The Equal-Life project is a perfect place to answer this, as we have a large amount of data.

Roos: In cities, the ways in which we move around from place to place are highly dependent on the road network. It is important to account for such dependencies while studying children's accessibility to greenspace. When we use road network measures to quantify home-based, school-based, or commute-based access to greenspaces, our results suggest size and shape, as well as the configuration and density of surrounding facilities, are key to hosting children's activities in green urban environments.

Sammie: In Equal-Life, combinations of early risk and protective factors are studied that can be related to mental health outcomes later in life. Identifying indicators and the children and/or environments that carry them will hopefully lead to future interventions to improve mental health outcomes, thereby contributing to public health. However, identifying and labelling groups of children at risk and/or the environments that can be of benefit or harm to them can also have harmful effects that should be mitigated. For example, it can cause worries and negative health effects in at-risk children and their parents.

Does your research have the potential to reshape how people raise their children?

Christoph: I hope so. Parents might not have the opportunity to react to our results. For example, the results might confirm that exposure to high levels of environmental noise combined with a lack of green areas where children live may have a negative effect on their cognitive development. However, the parents might need to

live in the given area because the rent is lower. If this is the case, the chances to react to such findings are very limited for parents with a lower income. If they cannot afford to move, they are forced to live in a place where more negative exposures occur. I think the main stakeholders of our results should be policymakers rather than parents.

Roos: Reading the ever-growing amount of research on the importance of urban greenspace for health and well-being, I hope this evidence inspires families to visit greenspaces regularly. I aim to empower cities to quantify the true value of vegetation in their urban jungles, so that they can structurally improve the quality of life for children in cities. Ideally, children simply encounter vegetation that suits their preferences in the places they visit in their daily routines.

Sammie: The findings of Equal-Life can improve the environments children grow up in, not only by the way people raise their children, but also by the way planners improve the environmental quality for them. There is still a taboo around many mental health issues, hopefully Equal-Life's results will contribute to breaking some of these taboos and to evoke (action). However, the sensitivity of the topic requires caution and thoughtfulness in communication to stakeholders. Parents and other stakeholders need to be consulted during our research to avoid results and interventions that do not match their needs, or worse, causes harm.

Vasileios: I aim to enable urban planners and policymakers to reshape

cities, neighbourhoods, and streets towards the creation of living environments which promote healthy behaviours and wellbeing. Admittedly, changing the urban environment could also affect the way people raise their children. For instance, feeling secure enough to encourage your child to walk around the neighbourhood and explore it without supervision could significantly change how children are raised. I would not attempt to say that my research, just by itself, has the potential to reshape how people raise their children. Instead, I hope that through my research I contribute knowledge on how to make urban environments healthier for children and people in general.

What are you most excited about when it comes to the future of this project?

Christoph: Right now, we are mainly developing different models to analyse data within the individual cohorts and school studies, while we are also harmonising data between cohorts for so-called meta-analyses. I am most excited for this upcoming stage, doing the meta-analyses, especially with regards to analysing the mechanisms leading to good mental health.

Roos: Most exciting about Equal-Life to me is how it aims to address the multitude of exposures together forming the exposome. Exposure to greenspace is only one of these, and I look forward to exploring with my fellow researchers how it connects to the exposome. How is the usage of greenspaces affected by urban safety? How do soundscapes or air quality

in greenspaces affect health? What interplay can we find between social exposures and opportunities for green play? These are questions I would love to answer!

Sammie: I am excited to be part of the Equal-Life research consortium and to work towards a better future for all children. I do this by reflecting on the ethical and societal dimensions of the research and by working on translating my results on ethical considerations into recommendations for the policy domain.

Vasileios: Equal-Life has brought together researchers working in different disciplines and talking in different “scientific languages” to work towards a common goal. What I am most excited to see is how all the different results and perspectives will be glued together and what newly discovered correlations between the different exposures and children’s mental health will emerge throughout this fascinating project.

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4.3 Equal-Life animation video

Written text spoken in the video:

Equal-Life: creating a healthier future for all children.
Before and after you are born, you feel, hear, eat, drink, see and breathe many things in your environment.
Inside the belly of your mother, the place where you are born, and the home where you grow up.
But it does not stop there.
Think about where you live, is there a lot of green space?
Are there many buildings around you, or many cars passing by?
And how is your social life?
Is your family big or small?
Do you feel cared for?
Do you feel safe?
Do you play with friends outside, or do you spend most of your time online?
Our environment contains things that interact with us and each other all the time.
Altogether, we call these things 'the Exposome'.
Remember the Green Park you like to play in?
This is part of your physical exposome.
And your friends in school?
They are part of your social exposome.
And you know what?
Our body and its functions can have an impact on your life too.
We call that the internal exposome.
The whole exposome influences our development and health, both positively and negatively.
This is what the project 'Equal-Life' is interested in: how the exposome affects the mental health and cognitive development of young people like you.

It is important to study this, because mental health challenges and difficulties in learning can have lifelong effects on young people's quality of life.

Also, the differences in health between people in Europe are growing.

This causes unfair differences in health and opportunities in the future for young people.

Equal life tries to understand how we can use knowledge about the exposome to make environments safer and healthier for them, instead of environments being a danger to young people's development and growth.

When we understand this relationship between the exposition and mental health and cognitive development, we can think of different ways to improve the environments of all children.

What do we need in order to do this?

We need information from children and young people in Europe about how they live, sleep, feel, eat, play and learn.

We also need researchers, cities, schools and health organizations to work together.

Equal-Life already has information for almost 250,000 young people from seven countries.

We will also collect new data in different countries and age groups.

Thanks to projects like Equal-Life, we will know better how to make living environments places where all children and adolescents will have equal opportunities and safeguard their future health.

We aim to create a healthy environment for young people.

Learn more about the project at: equal-life.eu or email us directly at: info@equal-life.eu.

5. References

<https://www.openaccessgovernment.org/studying-the-exposome-concept-for-a-healthier-future-for-all-children/136663/>

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